

PROSPECTIVE WAYS OF SERVICE INDUSTRIES

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the importance of service industries not only in the economy, but also in the social sphere, new types of services, changes in their share in the country's gross domestic product, and proposals and recommendations for the development of service industries.

The service sector covers all segments of the population and affects almost all socio-economic processes taking place in society, which shows how important and significant this issue is. In Uzbekistan, during the years of independence, systematic work was carried out on the rapid development of the service sector and services as one of the important directions and factors for diversifying the economy and deepening structural reforms, increasing employment, incomes and quality of life of the country's population. In addition, this sector plays an important role in ensuring sustainable economic growth.

In this regard, the task set in the resolution "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [1] to "actively develop small urban-type cities and towns through the creation of new industrial production and service centers, attracting funds from large economic associations, bank loans, and private foreign investments" will ensure the further development of this sector and further strengthen the reforms underway in this area.

There are also some problems in the formation and development of service sector entities and ensuring their high efficiency. The need to eliminate these problems and solve not only practical, but also a number of theoretical issues requires conducting research aimed at increasing the efficiency of this sector and ensuring the sustainable development of the socio-economic development of our country.

"The great economist Adam Smith, in order to more fully reveal the economic content of goods in the form of services and to solve the problem of considering them as a source of social wealth of the country, expressed his opinion on the concepts of productive labor and unproductive labor in his world-famous work "An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations". Thus, A. Smith distinguished between material and immaterial production and made a great contribution to the creation of the initial concept of service. The term service is used by scientists in economic literature from different points of view and is interpreted depending on the field of economic knowledge. Many foreign and domestic scientists have conducted theoretical research within the framework of this term. One of the famous scientists is F. Kotler, who defines service as follows: "A service is any activity that one party can offer to another." One of the famous scientists of our republic, I.S. Tukhliev, said:

“Services are a special type of intangible goods.” says, and in this approach, the scientist tries to emphasize that services represent the nature of commodities, that is, services reflect labor relations in the processes of production, material production, but the result of the production process has an intangible form.

A number of foreign and domestic scientists have conducted research on the topic, contributing to the development of various aspects of this field. Including: concepts, description and classification of services, analysis of the situation, their contribution to comfortable living conditions in the place of residence E.A. Razomasova, comments of local and foreign scientists on the concept of "service sector" V.A. Lazarev, direct and significant impact of the service sector on the health, mood, attitude to work, labor productivity of employees, level of satisfaction and joy with their lives, and in general, on the life and development of the productive forces M.M. Mukhammedov, processes of regulation and coordination of insurance services Zh.R. Zaynalov, growth rates of the service sector, newly emerging types of services, adaptation to market and consumer needs, and its importance in increasing the well-being of the population I.S. Tuxhliev, issues of service provision and its development in agriculture G.H. Kudratov, K.J. Mirzaev, M.K. Pardaev, R. Botirova, service, service and tourism development: problems and their solutions. I. Ochilov and others conducted research.

Economic and social analysis, logical approach, deduction and scientific study of the result were used, relying on a set of specific ways of knowing.

Today, the service sector plays an important role in the sustainable development of the economy. One of the founders of marketing theory, F. Kotler, said: “A service is any activity that one party can offer to another; as a result of which nothing is received. The provision of a service may be associated with a material product.

Sometimes it is difficult to distinguish between goods and services. In general, services have four characteristics: intangibility; impermanence; inseparability from the service provider and variability in quality. In addition, the service sector, as an integral part of the economy, has the following unique characteristics: - services are not tangible as tangible goods, and most service providers are individuals; - service providers are unique as individuals and cannot be separated or sold separately from their providers; - the quality of the service varies, that is, the service of one person can have different qualities at the same time and services do not appear as objects in the process of buying and selling; - the service cannot be stored and stored, but can only be consumed during the service; - the service itself cannot be moved from one place to another without being separated from its owner, but the production and consumption of the service occur simultaneously; -service providers and consumers may be directly involved in the service process, etc.

These aspects, in addition to the generally recognized features on a global scale, also include features that are relevant to the development of our country. It should also be noted that the invisibility of services means that we cannot observe them - they cannot be displayed, transported, stored, packaged (packaged) or studied after purchase. By their very nature, the services market develops according to the laws of a market economy and is part of the goods market. At the same time, it has a number of its own characteristics, requiring a special approach to meeting the demand for services in entrepreneurial and marketing activities. Services are both an economic and a social sphere at the same time. Because the activities of the service industry are used in all areas, including economic, social and even political spheres. The economic sectorality of services is manifested in the fact that a part of the country's gross domestic product is created in this sphere. Its social sphere is that most of it is aimed at improving people's lives and making their lives more convenient. As a result of this service being directly integrated into the communication service, modern paid services - remittance channels (Paynet, Unipay, Western-union, etc.) have been formed. The development of the services market in the republic serves as an incubator for entrepreneurship. Because, due to

the rapid turnover of capital, favorable conditions are created for business entrepreneurship. The structure of the services market in most cases consists of small enterprises, which allows the majority of economically active persons to engage in business. The services market represents the purchase and sale relations for the provision of household, educational, medical, technical, communal, cultural, communication, transport, consulting, engineering, leasing and other services to the population. It also forms its own branches and institutions. This, in turn, is an important guarantee of the formation of the middle class of owners (entrepreneurs) and is the basis for the development of the country's economy. Therefore, it is appropriate to consider the economic analysis of the reforms being carried out in the service sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the processes of their implementation and the results. The fact that the service sector accounted for 47.3 percent of the gross domestic product in 2017 indicates how significant the role and influence of this sector in our economy are. It is worth noting that, given that today more than half of the employed population in the entire economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan works in the service sector, it is necessary to act now for the prospects of the sector.

Conclusions and suggestions In conclusion, the experience of developed countries shows that private entrepreneurship, especially service sector entities, is one of the main factors ensuring socio-economic stability in all aspects of social development. The development of this sector leads to the enrichment of the country's population, economic development, consumer market saturation, an increase in state budget revenues, and a decrease in unemployment. It is also necessary to practically substantiate the fact that one of the important directions for increasing the efficiency of the service sector is the efficiency of economic potential and develop a system of indicators expressing them, as well as ways to identify and analyze the factors affecting their change; - identify and analyze the factors affecting private enterprises engaged in the service sector; - show that, based on the importance of determining the break-even point of the service sector today, a number of methods can be used and show ways to increase efficiency by analyzing the factors affecting its change; - improvement of standardization, licensing and certification systems in increasing the efficiency of the service sector; - based on the importance of increasing the profit and profitability of the service sector in the conditions of a free economy, by analyzing the factors affecting their change, to show the ways to find internal opportunities for improving these indicators.

The "New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026" sets out many goals and objectives. Based on these goals and objectives, it is necessary to continue the coherence of these reforms, in particular, to systematically develop the service sector in the future. Therefore, we believe that it is appropriate to make a number of proposals for the development of this sector in the current digital economy. Based on these goals and objectives, it is necessary to continue the coherence of these reforms, in particular, to systematically develop the service sector in the future. Therefore, we believe that it is appropriate to make a number of proposals for the development of this sector in the current new era of economic development. Firstly, to expand the scope of modern market services, create a positive competitive environment in the sector by introducing new types of services, and dramatically increase the share of the sector in the national economy of the country. For this, it is necessary to further increase the efficiency of the service sector and turn the service sector into a driver of the economy.

Used literature :

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